

than one in the complex. The lower value of f and higher value of hx indicated covalent nature of the metal-ligand bond.

Cobalt(II) complex showed three d-d bands in the region 11 494, 16 129 and 19 230 cm^{-1} which may be attributed to transitions, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F) (\nu_1)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F) (\nu_2)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P) (\nu_3)$, respectively. The values of ν_1 , ν_2 and ν_3 may be obtained by Konig's equations¹⁰. The values of 10 Dq and B were calculated¹¹. The ratio $\nu_2(\text{obs})/\nu_1(\text{calcd.})$ was found to be 2.01 as required for octahedral cobalt(II) complexes. Calculated 10 Dq value was in good agreement to that determined by $\nu_2(\text{obs}) - \nu_1(\text{calcd.})$. The β_{35} value in the range 0.69-0.99 clearly indicated the partial covalent character of the metal-ligand bond.

The electronic spectrum of the complex, $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_2\text{N})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ was consistent with octahedral geometry. The d-d bands at 13 698, 23 895 and 28 571 cm^{-1} were assignable to the ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F) (\nu_1)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F) (\nu_2)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P) (\nu_3)$ transitions, respectively¹². The inter-electronic repulsion parameter B and other ligand field parameters 10 Dq , β_{35} and λ were calculated as usual^{13,14}. The ν_2/ν_1 ratio was found to be 1.74 as against 1.80 (theoretical)¹⁴. The lower value of ν_2/ν_1 indicated distortion of the octahedral geometry. The β_{35} value in the range 0.53-1.20 indicated covalent nature of the metal-ligand bond.

Three shoulder bands at 13 157, 14 925 and 25 641 cm^{-1} in the electronic spectra of the complex $[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_2\text{N})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ were assigned to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ transitions, respectively, showing distorted octahedral geometry¹⁵ in the complex.

Antibacterial screening: All the compounds were tested for their antibacterial activity by disc-diffusion method in DMF and found to be active against *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *B. subtilis*, *S. veridance* and *P. vulgaris*. The highest dilution of the test compounds which inhibited the visual growth of the test organisms was taken as the minimum inhibitory concentration ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$). The results are presented in Table 1.

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Cobalt(II), Nickel(II), Copper(II), Zinc(II), Cadmium(II) and Mercury(II) Complexes with *N,N'*-Bis(benzoin)-4,4'-diamino-3,3'-dimethyldiphenylmethane

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IN continuation of earlier studies¹⁻⁴ on the Schiff base complexes of divalent metal ions, the present communication reports the synthesis of a new (O, N, N, O) tetradentate Schiff base ligand, *N,N'*-bis(benzoin)-4,4'-diamino-3,3'-dimethyldiphenylmethane and its complexation behaviour with Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} .

Experimental

All the chemicals were of A.R. grade.

Preparation of ligand: To the ethanolic solution of benzoin (4.2 g, 0.02 mol) and 4,4'-diamino-3,3'-dimethyldiphenylmethane (2.3 g, 0.01 mol), anhydrous sodium acetate (4 g) was added and the reaction mixture refluxed over a water-bath for 2 h. The hot solution was then poured into ice-cold water with stirring when the light yellow coloured Schiff base separated out. It was allowed to stand for 24 h and then filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallised from ethanol (95%), m.p. 115° (Found: C, 82.67; H, 5.92; N, 4.28. $\text{C}_{43}\text{H}_{38}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$ calcd. for: C, 84.03; H, 6.18; N, 4.56%).

Preparation of complexes: To the ethanolic solution of metal chlorides (0.01 mol), the ligand solution (0.01 mol) in ethanol was added separately and the reaction mixture refluxed over a water-bath for ~0.5 h. On cooling, concentrated NH_4OH was added dropwise with stirring when the metal

NOTES

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, AND PHYSICAL, DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Colour	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		Λ_M $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	μ_{eff} B.M.	Mol. wt. Found/(Calcd.)
			Metals	N			
LH ₂	Light yellow	115	—	4.28 (4.56)	—	—	572 (614)
[CoL(H ₂ O) ₅]	Pink	120	7.92 (8.33)	3.64 (3.96)	5.5	5.1	658 (706.9)
[NiL(H ₂ O) ₅]	Green	135	7.97 (8.30)	3.72 (3.96)	7.8	3.1	664 (706.7)
[Cu ₂ LCl(H ₂ O) ₄]	Blue	>250	14.07 (14.30)	3.02 (3.17)	4.6	1.3	842 (882)
[ZnL(H ₂ O)]	White	225	8.85 (9.13)	3.76 (4.02)	5.8	—	653 (695.3)
[CdL]	White	>250	15.24 (15.51)	3.42 (3.66)	7.5	—	674 (724.4)
[HgL]	White	210	24.18 (24.66)	3.48 (3.44)	6.5	—	767 (812.6)

* LH₂ = *N,N'*-Bis(benzoin)-4,4'-diamino-3,3'-dimethyldiphenylmethane.

chelates separated out. The compounds were then filtered, washed with ethanol and ether, and dried in vacuum.

Elemental analyses, molecular weight (in camphor, Rast) molar conductivity in acetone and DMF, magnetic moment at room temperature, ir spectra (KBr), electronic spectra (MeOH, for Cu complex in DMF) of the complexes were determined (Table 1).

Results and Discussion

The complexes have the stoichiometry [ML. 2H₂O], [Cu₂LCl₂.4H₂O], [ZnL.H₂O] and [M'L], where M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}; M' = Cd^{II}, Hg^{II}; LH₂ = *N,N'*-bis(benzoin)-4,4'-diamino-3,3'-dimethyldiphenylmethane. The cobalt complex is pink, nickel complex green, copper complex blue and zinc, cadmium and mercury complexes are white. Low Δ_M values in acetone and DMF medium suggest their non-electrolytic nature.

A strong ir band at 2 800 cm⁻¹ for the ligand assignable to ν_{OH} , is lowered due to O—H...N intramolecular hydrogen bonding. The absence of this band in metal complexes indicates the deprotonation of alcoholic OH groups. In case of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes the presence of coordinated water is indicated by the appearance of a broad double hump at ca. 3 200–3 300 cm⁻¹ supported by an additional peak at ca. 840–850 cm⁻¹ attributable to OH stretching and wagging, respectively. A sharp ir band at 1 660 cm⁻¹ in the ligand assignable to $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ is lowered to ~1 650 cm⁻¹ in the metal chelates indicating the bonding of imine nitrogen atoms to the metal ions^{5,6}. The $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ in the ligand appearing at 1 260 cm⁻¹ is shifted to ~1 250 cm⁻¹ in the metal chelates. This lowering of $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ by ~10 cm⁻¹ shows that the Schiff base is also linked to the metal ions through both of its hydroxylic oxygen atoms. The conclusive evidence of bonding of the ligand molecule is provided by the appearance of the bands at ~450 and 510 cm⁻¹ assignable⁷ to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$, respectively. The

composition of the copper(II) complex suggests the

presence of Cu bridging modes as evident

from the presence of a band at 260 cm⁻¹ and absence of terminal Cu—Cl bonding⁸ at ~300 cm⁻¹.

The magnetic moment of cobalt(II) complex (5.1 B.M.) is indicative of octahedral geometry. The electronic spectra cobalt(II) complex showed three bands at 8 400(10), 18 450(25) and 20 200(34) cm⁻¹ attributed to ⁴T_{1g}(F)→⁴T_{2g}(F), ⁴T_{1g}(F)→⁴A_{2g}(F) and ⁴T_{1g}(F)→⁴T_{1g}(P) transitions, respectively, in conformity with an octahedral configuration⁹ supported by the high μ_{eff} value. The magnetic moment of nickel(II) complex is 3.1 B.M. which indicate the presence of two unpaired electrons. The electronic spectra of the complex showed three bands at 9 450, 15 200 and 23 600 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to ³A_{2g}→³T_{2g}(F), ³A_{2g}→³T_{1g}(F) and ³A_{2g}→³T_{1g}(P) transitions, respectively, in the O_h symmetry. The copper(II) complex shows subnormal magnetic moment (μ_{eff} =1.38 B.M.) indicating halogen bridged dimeric structure¹⁰ of the copper(II) complex. The absorption spectra of this complex shows a broad asymmetric band at 15 400 cm⁻¹ suggesting a distorted octahedral configuration^{11,12}. Molecular weight data of the Cu^{II} complex are in conformity with a dimeric structure of the complex. The rest of the complexes are monomeric in nature which is evident from their molecular weight data (Table 1). The zinc complex is suggested to be pentacoordinated, most likely square-pyramidal, which is achieved by the presence of the water molecule in the axial position of the complex. Thus cadmium(II) and mercury(II) complexes are four-coordinated having tetrahedral geometry around the metal ions, as supported by conductance, ir spectra and molecular weight data.

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Dioxouranium(II) and Thorium(IV) Complexes with Multidentate Schiff Bases derived from 1,8-Diaminonaphthalene

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HERE we report the dioxouranium(II) and thorium(IV) complexes with Schiff bases obtained by the condensation of 1,8-diaminonaphthalene with benzaldehyde (1), salicylaldehyde (2) and vanillin (3).

- 1; R=R'=H (DAN-Benz)
2; R=OH, R'=H (DAN-Sal)
3; R=OH, R'=OCH₃ (DAN-Van)

Experimental

Hydrated thorium(IV) nitrate, uranyl nitrate hexahydrate (B.D.H.) and 1,8-diaminonaphthalene (Fluka) were used. Benzaldehyde, salicylaldehyde and vanillin were used after purification. The ligands were prepared according to the literature methods¹.

Synthesis of complexes: Equimolar quantities of uranyl or thorium nitrate in ethanol were refluxed with the ligand in ethanol for ~1 h. The coloured complexes separated on cooling. The complexes formed were suction-filtered, washed thoroughly with ethanol, then with ether and finally dried in vacuum over fused calcium chloride.

Uranium and thorium contents in complexes were determined gravimetrically² as U₂O₈ and ThO₂. Nitrogen was estimated microanalytically by Dumas' method.

Physicochemical measurements: Conductance measurements were done with Elico CM-82 conductivity bridge using DMF as solvent. Infrared spectra (KBr) of the complexes and ligands were recorded with a Perkin-Elmer 81 spectrometer in the region 4000–180 cm⁻¹. The results are presented in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The limited solubility of complexes in common organic solvents did not permit the determination of their molecular weights, low molar conductance values indicate the complexes to be non-electrolytes³.

An examination of the IR spectra of the free ligand and those of complexes indicated similarity although in many cases the ligand bands were shifted due to lattice effects or due to departure from idealised symmetry^{4,5}. The IR spectra of ligands 2 and 3 show a broad weak band at ~2900 cm⁻¹ instead of a strong band at ~3100 cm⁻¹ due to the phenolic OH group. This may be due to the intra-molecular hydrogen bonding between hydroxyl hydrogen and nitrogen of the azomethine group forming the stable six membered ring⁶. The complexes of Sl. nos. 2, 3, 5 and 6 (Table 1) also do not show the OH group frequency thereby indicating that the OH group of the Schiff base 2 and 3 is utilised in the formation of M—O bond. This is further supported by the shift of C—O frequency from ~1290 cm⁻¹ to ~1380 cm⁻¹ in these complexes^{6,7}. A strong band found in the region 1620–1590 cm⁻¹ is assignable to the C=N stretch of Schiff bases. The shifting of the ν_{C=N} to high frequency region (1640–1630 cm⁻¹) in complexes suggests the coordination to the central metal atom through the nitrogen of the azomethine group^{6,7}. As expected^{8,9} the ν₃ and ν₁ vibrational modes of uranyl ions in complexes of Sl. nos. 1–3 (Table 1) appeared at 935–925 and 835–820 cm⁻¹,